

Chemical Investigation of *Cocculus Hirsutus* (Linn) Diels

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Chemical investigation of *Cocculus hirsutus* affords an essential oil, β -sitosterol, ginnol, an inositol derivative, and two alkaloids characterised as picrates. In addition, a colorless wax and an appreciable amount of a viscous oil have been obtained.

The plant *Cocculus hirsutus* (Linn) Diels (Syn. *Cocculus villosus* D.C.), commonly known as *Vasanvalli* (Sanskrit—*Jaljamani* or *Patalgarudi*), is a semiwoody climber, indigenous to the tropical countries, and belongs to the family *Menispermaceae*. It is common in hedges throughout the State of Maharashtra, specially in the lower altitudes of the Western Ghats.

The whole of the plant is used in the Ayurvedic system of medicine¹ for a variety of diseases. The roots are used in cases of rheumatism, fevers, and digestive disorders. The juice of the leaves is efficacious in gonorrhoea and is used externally as a soothing application against eczema, impetigo, etc. The plant is also useful against tuberculosis².

As both the roots and the leaves are used for different purposes, the chemical investigation of both was undertaken separately.

From the petroleum ether extract of the roots, the residue after removal of the solvent gave a very small amount of an essential oil which yielded a crystalline 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone. Chromatographic separation of the residue after steam distillation or of the petrol ether extract over alumina yielded in addition to a yellow viscous oil, a colorless, neutral solid of m.p. 142° which gave all the colour reactions of a sterol. It was identified as β -sitosterol by a mixed m.p. determination and by preparation of acetyl and benzoyl derivatives.

Ether and chloroform extracts of the roots failed to give any other product except β -sitosterol and a reddish viscous oil which could not be purified.

The methanol extract of the roots (vide Experimental) afforded small amounts of a colorless, crystalline, neutral substance of m.p. 228°. It did not contain any nitrogen and its analysis conformed to $C_7H_{14}O_6$ confirmed by its molecular weight determined cryoscopically. The compound is easily soluble in water but insoluble in organic solvents. It is optically inactive and can be recovered unchanged on boiling with hydrochloric acid. It did not reduce Fehling's solution and failed to give the characteristic tests for carbohydrates. It readily reduced ammoniacal silver nitrate solution, indicating it to be a polyhydroxy compound. Attempts to prepare acetyl or benzoyl derivatives yielded oily mix-

1. Nadkarny, "Indian Materia Medica", 1954, Vol. I, p. 362.

2. Chopra, "Indigenous Drugs of India", 1958,

tures. The composition and the properties of the substance indicate it to be an inositol derivative, probably sequoyitol (m.p. 234°), which is found to occur in a number of plants.³

The methanolic extract also showed presence of glucose, identified by paper chromatography. In addition, an alkaloidal fraction was isolated from which two picrates of m.p. 208-10° and 195-6° could be prepared, the latter in very poor yields. The free base obtained from the former picrate is an amorphous powder, melting indefinitely. Other salts, such as the hydrochloride or sulphate, could not be prepared. Alkali fusion or zinc dust distillation of the alkaloid also failed to furnish any definite product.

The petroleum ether extract of the whole plant on chromatographic separation over alumina afforded in addition to a colorless wax and a viscous yellow oil, three colorless nitrogen-free substances: (i) m.p. 104°, (ii) 80-82°, and (iii) 142°. The compound (i) did not give the usual reactions for a phytosterol or for a carbonyl function. It was in too small an amount for further work.

The compound (ii) contained one hydroxyl group as was indicated by active hydrogen determination and the formation of a mono-acetyl derivative. On oxidation with dichromate in presence of sulphuric acid, (ii) was oxidised to a ketone which readily formed an oxime. From the analytical and above data it appeared that (ii) could either be heptacosanol or ginnol, both of which occur freely in nature.⁴ To determine the structure of (ii), heptacosanol, and its acetyl derivative, heptacosanone and its oxime were prepared from myristic acid.⁴ All the four are found to be different from (ii) or its corresponding derivatives indicating (ii) to be ginnol which occurs in opium and in the plant *Ginkgo biloba* L. which is claimed to possess insecticidal properties. The compound (ii) is identical as shown by mixed m.p. with the substance isolated by Davis and Rose⁵ from the roots of various species of *Lithospermum* which has been claimed to reduce the incidence of spontaneous mammary tumours in susceptible animals.

The substance (iii) was identified as β -sitosterol by the preparation of its acetyl derivative and a mixed melting point determination.

The methanolic extract of the whole plant afforded β -sitosterol, a dark viscous oil, and a colorless substance of m.p. 228°, identical with that obtained from the roots.

Extraction of the plant with 1% hydrochloric acid or ethanolic acetic acid failed to provide a pure substance.

EXPERIMENTAL

The roots and the whole plant of *Cocculus hirsutus* were collected locally during the months of December and January and identified botanically and supplied to us by Mr. P. V. Bole, St. Xavier's College, Bombay.

3. Karrer, "Constitution and Occurrence of Organic Plant Products", 1958, p. 114.

4. Kipping, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1890, 57, 981; Shu Furukawa, *Bull. Inst. Phys. Chem. Res. Tokyo*, 1929, 8, 62.

5. *Chem. & Ind.*, 1955, 1739.

Petroleum Ether Extract of the Roots

Expt. 1.—The powdered roots (2.27 kg.) were soaked for about a month in petroleum ether (11.7 litres, b.p. 40-60°). The pasty residue (4.8 g.) left after removal of the solvent under vacuum was steam distilled to give an essential oil (45 mg.). It was twice distilled at 127-37°/0.02 mm. (C, 45.2%; H, 5.1%; n_D^{20} 1.5011). A 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone from the oil crystallised from dilute alcohol in orange needles, m.p. 115-7°.

A dark brown oil (3.5 g.) left after steam distillation was chromatographed over alumina (105 g.) (standardised according to Brockmann and supplied by E. Merck).

Fractions eluted with petroleum ether (40-60°) consisted only of a yellowish wax. Fractions eluted with petroleum ether and benzene mixture (1:10) gave a viscous yellow oil which could not be distilled till 250° under vacuum.

From the fractions eluted with benzene-ether (3:1), a colorless solid was isolated, which after repeated crystallisations from methanol-acetone yielded needles, m.p. 142-43°. [α] $_D^{25}$ -36°. M.W. 404. (Found: C, 84.0; H, 12.2; active H, 0.24. $C_{29}H_{50}O$ requires C, 83.6; H, 11.9; active H 0.33%). The compound gave a positive Libermann-Burchard test. Its acetyl derivative, prepared by refluxing with acetic anhydride, gave needles from methanol-acetone, m.p. 131-32°. (Found: C, 81.3; H, 11.8. $C_{31}H_{52}O_2$ requires C, 81.6; H, 11.4%). The benzoyl derivative obtained by heating with benzoyl chloride after crystallisation from methanol had m.p. 144-5°. (Found: C, 82.7; H, 10.4. $C_{35}H_{54}O_2$ requires C, 82.9; H, 10.6%). The compound was identified as β -sitosterol by a mixed melting point determination.

Expt. 2.—The petroleum ether extract from 6 kg. of roots after removal of the solvent was directly chromatographed over alumina. Only substances described under Expt. 1 were obtained.

Expt. 3.—The petroleum ether extract was divided into acidic, basic, and neutral fractions. Only β -sitosterol and a yellow viscous oil were isolated.

Ether and Chloroform Extracts of the Roots

The roots (4.54 kg.) were extracted with ether (36.5 litres) for 30 days at room temperature. The pasty residue (9 g.) after removal of the solvent afforded minute quantities of an essential oil (same as in Expt. 1) on steam distillation and a yellow wax, β -sitosterol, and a brown viscous oil on chromatographic separation.

The material left after extraction with ether was triturated with chloroform (9 litres) for 15 days. The residual dark viscous oil (about 8 g.) on chromatography yielded besides a reddish oil a small amount of a colorless solid which did not give the colour tests for sterols and which after repeated crystallisations from methanol had m.p. 129-35°. It could not be investigated further.

Methanol Extract of the Roots

Expt. 4.—The roots (2.27 kg.) were extracted with methanol (22.75 litres) for 20 days when a brown paste (50 g.) was obtained as residue on distillation of the solvent.

About half of this (20 g.) was divided into acidic, basic, and neutral fractions. No pure substance could be isolated from any of these fractions.

The remaining part (30 g.) was chromatographed over alumina when only a brownish viscous oil, which could not be distilled to 250° under vacuum (0.1 mm), was isolated.

Expt. 5.—The material (about 6 kg.) left over after extraction with chloroform was triturated with methanol for several days. Distillation of the solvent under vacuum yielded a reddish semisolid which was filtered. Treatment of the latter with small amounts of methanol gave an insoluble granular product (150 mg.) which easily dissolved in water. Its aqueous solution was boiled with charcoal and the filtrate evaporated under vacuum when colorless crystals, m.p. 225-26°, separated. After repeated crystallisations from aqueous methanol the m.p. rose to 226-28°. (Found: C, 43.6; H, 7.3; 7.2; OMe, 15.1. C₇H₁₄O₆ requires C, 43.3; H, 7.20; OMe, 16%). The compound was optically inactive and its molecular weight by cryoscopic method was 189. It was recovered unchanged on boiling with hydrochloric acid or phenylhydrazine solution and did not respond to the Molisch test for carbohydrates. It did not reduce Fehling's solution but readily gave a silver mirror test. Attempts to prepare acetyl or benzoyl derivative yielded oily mixtures. The compound is probably a methyl ether of inositol.

The methanolic filtrate from Expt. (5) left a residue (about 14 g.) which gave positive Meyer's and Burchardat's tests for alkaloids and also reduced Fehling's solution.

The residue was divided into 3 portions (a), (b), and (c).

From (a) only glucose was identified by running a paper chromatogram using butanol-acetic acid as the solvent mixture.

Part (b) (about 8 g.) was subjected to chromatography, using alumina, silica gel, and cellulose powder as adsorbents in different experiments. Elution with different solvents in all cases failed to furnish a pure substance.

Part (c) (about 7 g.) was treated with water when an almost clear solution was obtained. It was filtered and the filtrate extracted successively with ethyl acetate, chloroform, and chloroform-methanol mixture.

The ethyl acetate extract gave negative tests for alkaloids and sugars. On chromatography traces of a colorless solid, which crystallised from methanol in needles, m.p. 262°, were obtained. (Found: C, 62.17; H, 9.03%).

The chloroform extract, which gave positive tests for alkaloids, was treated with an ethanolic solution of picric acid, when a brown picrate separated. After repeated crystallisations from ethanol it melted at 209-10°. (Found: C, 55.9; H, 4.0; N, 10.0%). The picrate was suspended in chloroform and decomposed with lithium hydroxide. The chloroform layer was washed thrice with lithium hydroxide and water and then dried over sodium sulphate. Distillation of the solvent left a brown amorphous residue, m.p. >240°. Attempts to prepare other salts from it failed to give pure substances. Alkali fusion of the above alkaloid did not give a pure substance. Zinc-dust distillation yielded traces of a colorless oil (b.p. 80-85°/0.02 mm) which gave variable results on analysis.

The chloroform-methanol extract on treatment with picric acid gave a solid which after several crystallisations from ethanol had m.p. 195-96°. It too insufficient for further work.

Petroleum Ether Extract of the Whole Plant

The plant material (8 kg.) was extracted with petroleum ether (35.1 litres). The residue (60 g.) was chromatographed over alumina. Elution with different solvents was effected and about 80 fractions were collected.

Fractions 1-7 eluted with petroleum ether yielded about 5 g. of a colorless wax.

Fractions 8-16 also eluted with the same solvent gave a wax together with small amounts of a colorless, neutral, nitrogen-free substance which after repeated crystallisations from benzene-acetone had m.p. 104°. (Found: C, 77.5; H, 13.63. $C_{24}H_{46}O_2$ requires C, 77.8; H, 13.6%; $C_{22}H_{46}O_2$ requires C, 77.2; H, 13.53%). From the composition and the properties of the substance it could either be tetracosan diol or dicosan diol.

Fractions 27-38 eluted with a mixture of petroleum ether and benzene (3:1) yielded a colorless neutral substance which after crystallisations from methanol had m.p. 80-82°. (Found: C, 81.7; H, 14.1; 'H', 0.23%).

The acetyl derivative after crystallisation from methanol had m.p. 47-48°. (Found: C, 79.6; H, 13.2%). From a reference to literature, the compound could either be the alcohol heptacosanol ($C_{27}H_{56}O$) or ginnol ($C_{29}H_{60}O$).

Oxidation of the Compound.—The compound (150 mg.) was suspended in hot water (25 ml) and to this were added potassium dichromate (165 mg.) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 1 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 2 hours and repeatedly extracted with ether. Removal of the solvent left a colorless residue (90 mg.) which crystallised from methanol in needles. m.p. 73-74°. (Found: C, 81.8; H, 14.0%).

The oxime from the above ketone was crystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. 45-46°. (Found: N, 3.2%).

Preparation of Myristone.—It was obtained from myristic acid according to Kipping⁶, m.p. 72-74°. Its oxime had m.p. 48-49°. The mixed m.p. of myristone and its oxime with those of the above ketone and its oxime showed a definite lowering.

Reduction of Myristone to Heptacosanol.—Myristone (150 mg.) was reduced with $LiAlH_4$ (300 mg.) in dry ether (100 ml) by refluxing for 2 hours. Colorless needles (80 mg.), m.p. 83-84°, from ethanol were obtained. The acetyl derivative crystallised from methanol, m.p. 44-45°.

The mixed melting points of heptacosanol¹¹ and its acetyl derivative with the alcohol and its acetyl derivative obtained from plant material were lowered, indicating the plant alcohol to be ginnol.

Fractions 39-63 of the chromatogram gave on elution with different solvents a viscous yellow oil together with β -sitosterol.

Methanol Extract.—The plant material (2.3 kg.) was extracted with methanol (22.75 litres) for 8 days. The extract on concentration gave a dark precipitate which on chromatography over alumina yielded ginnol, β -sitosterol, a solid of m.p. 119-20° and a large amount of viscous oil.

Methanolic filtrate deposited on keeping crystals, m.p. 228 . (C, 43.4; H, 7.3%) identical with that obtained from the roots.

A 1% acid extract of the roots or the whole plant failed to give any pure substance.

The microanalyses were carried out at the Institute by Mr. R. S. Kulkarni and by Mr. W. Manser, Zurich, to whom the authors are thankful. They also thank the Maharashtra State Industrial Research Committee for a research grant.